

Fake News Detection: A Comparative Analysis of RNN LSTM and Decision Tree Algorithms for Nonlinear Relationships

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Fake news is about false or misleading information delivered as real news. It has risen in the digital era as a threat because it can manipulate peoples' opinions. Fake news detection is very subjective and relative to the context. It can be detected by text classification models and achieve high accuracy based on the labeled data set, suitable algorithms and processing techniques. The model should be able to understand the pattern between reliable and fake news. It should differentiate the nature of the fake news. Finding minute pattern differentiation in fake and reliable news can be possible with a large number of input data. Therefore, authors proposed a machine learning-based approach to detect fake news. The well-established labeled dataset consists of fake and reliable news taken and concatenated into single. Then followed the text classification preprocessing techniques and split the tokenized sequence into the training and testing sets. For RNN (Recurrent Neural Network) bidirectional LSTM (Long Short Term Memory), gensim preprocessing was taken and trained on the model. The same thing happened for the Decision tree model, but it was replaced by TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) feature. Gensim is used in LSTM for capturing bidirectional dependencies in sequential data, while TF-IDF is chosen for the Decision Tree which is suited for structured data. Both models' accuracy, precision, and recall were taken for comparison. Both algorithms showcased promising results in identifying fake news texts. RNN LSTM achieved a remarkable accuracy of 99.86%, outperforming the Decision Tree's accuracy of 99.68%. The RNN LSTM lies in its capability to capture nonlinear relationships within text data, which is crucial for understanding the context and flow of information in fake news detection. While Decision Trees offer interpretability, it faces difficulty with intricate nonlinear patterns in text. Results prove that RNN LSTM can do accurate and context-aware fake news detection.

Keywords: Decision tree algorithm, Fake news detection, Nonlinear relationships, RNN LSTM, Text classification